

Socio-cognitive determinants of lifestyle behavior in the context of dementia risk reduction: a population-based study in the Netherlands

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1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Unhealthy behavior increases the risk of dementia. Various socio-cognitive determinants
3 influence whether individuals persist in or alter these unhealthy behaviors.

4 **Objective:** This study identifies relevant determinants of behavior associated to dementia risk.

5 **Methods:** 4,104 Dutch individuals (40-79 years) completed a screening questionnaire exploring
6 lifestyle behaviors associated with dementia risk. Subsequently, 3,065 respondents who actively
7 engaged in one or more unhealthy behaviors completed a follow-up questionnaire investigating socio-
8 cognitive determinants of these behaviors. Cross-tables were used to assess the accuracy of participants'
9 perceptions regarding their behavior compared to recommendations. Confidence Interval-Based
10 Estimation of Relevance (CIBER) was used to identify the most relevant determinants of behavior based
11 on visual inspection and interpretation.

12 **Results:** Among the respondents, 91.3% reported at least one, while 65% reported two or more
13 unhealthy lifestyle behaviors associated to dementia risk. Many of them were not aware they did not
14 adhere to lifestyle recommendations. The most relevant determinants identified include attitudes (i.e.,
15 lacking a passion for cooking and finding pleasure in drinking alcohol or smoking), misperceptions on
16 social comparisons (i.e., overestimating healthy diet intake and underestimating alcohol intake), and
17 low perceived behavioral control (i.e., regarding changing physical inactivity, altering diet patterns, and
18 smoking cessation).

19 **Conclusion:** Individual-level interventions that encourage lifestyle change should prioritize on
20 enhancing accurate perceptions of behaviors compared to recommendations, while strengthening
21 perceived control towards behavior change. Given the high prevalence of dementia risk factors,
22 combining interventions at both individual and environmental levels are likely the most effective
23 strategy to reduce dementia on a population scale.

24 *Keywords: Prevention, Dementia, Public Health, Health Promotion, Health Risk Behaviors, Behavioral*
25 *Medicine, Alzheimer's Disease*

26

27 **1. Background**

28 A growing body of evidence has identified modifiable risk and protective factors for dementia [1, 2].
29 These insights pave the way for the development of individual and environmental level preventive
30 interventions to reduce the rising total prevalence of dementia. The current strategy strongly revolves
31 around multidomain approaches to encourage healthy lifestyle changes among individuals at-risk [3],
32 particularly in middle and older age. Across the lifespan, a wide variety of modifiable lifestyle factors
33 have been associated with dementia risk [1], such as physical inactivity, unhealthy diet, psychological
34 stress, smoking, low sleep quality, and limited social and cognitive stimulating activities [4-6]. All these
35 lifestyle factors are partly influenced by behavior specific socio-cognitive determinants that determine
36 if individuals persist in or alter their behavior [7, 8]. Examples of socio-cognitive determinants are
37 attitudes (i.e., a latent disposition or tendency to respond with favorableness or unfavorableness to a
38 behavior), social norms (i.e., the perceived social pressure to perform or not perform a behavior), and
39 perceived behavioral control (i.e., the perceived degree of being capable of, or have control over,
40 performing a behavior) [9].

41 These socio-cognitive determinants influence behavioral choices, yet environmental factors also play a
42 pivotal role. The environment can impact behavior directly as well as indirectly by influencing socio-
43 cognitive determinants, underscoring the complexity of behavior change [8]. While there is extensive
44 literature on determinants of behavior [8], insights into the specific determinants relevant to dementia
45 risk reduction are limited. For example, the Motivation to Change Lifestyle and Health Behaviors for
46 Dementia Risk Reduction Scale (MCLHB-DRR) offers understanding of determinants of generic
47 lifestyle change [10], without delving into determinants of specific behaviors, such as attitudes about
48 diet or self-efficacy towards smoking cessation [10]. This represents a limitation, as individuals are
49 often more positive towards broader lifestyle change than to altering particular unhealthy behaviors
50 [11]. Furthermore, it is well-known that determinants are highly behavior specific, which makes it
51 impossible to intuitively select relevant determinants, even for experts in behavior change [12].

52 With this study, we aim to obtain a better understanding of relevant socio-cognitive determinants in the
53 context of dementia risk reduction, to inform the selection of appropriate behavior change methods to

54 change these determinants through interventions [7, 8]. The current focus is primarily at the individual
55 level, as this research is part of a larger project that includes a clinical trial on a digitally supported
56 lifestyle program to promote brain health among older adults (LETHE, clinicaltrials.gov identifier
57 NCT05565170) [13, 14]. Nevertheless, the findings may offer valuable insights for new research to
58 explore how environmental factors influence behavior directly and through socio-cognitive
59 determinants [15, 16].

60

61 **Methods**

62 In this cross-sectional study, we used a screening questionnaire to identify individuals with room to
63 improve their lifestyle behavior and we invited them for a follow-up questionnaire to explore socio-
64 cognitive determinants of these behaviors. The study protocol was pre-registered [17] and materials and
65 data to replicate the findings are open access available [18]. The findings are reported using the
66 Strengthening the Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) checklist [19].

67 ***2.1 Recruitment***

68 In September 2022, respondents were recruited via the ISO-certified Internet research agency
69 Flycatcher that has a large panel in the Netherlands. Dutch speaking respondents aged 40 to 79 years
70 were eligible for participation because lifestyle behavior is associated with dementia in mid-life and
71 late-life [20, 21].

72 A sample size estimation indicated that at least 4,000 respondents were required for the screening
73 questionnaire to ensure sufficient statistical power for analyses using data from the follow-up. This
74 estimation accounted for population prevalence of lifestyle behaviors (i.e., smoking had the lowest
75 population prevalence, $\approx 20\%$ [22]), the response rate expectancy of Flycatcher ($\approx 75\%$), and the ability
76 to detect correlations coefficients of .2 with half-width of .1 using confidence interval of 95% [23]).

77 ***2.2 Questionnaire development***

78 Questionnaires were developed through triangulation with literature, an interview study ($n=23$) [11],
79 and think-aloud sessions with experts in dementia risk reduction ($n=4$). The questionnaires were pre-

80 tested with three middle-aged and older individuals of low socio-economic status (SES) who participate
81 in an advisory board consulting on research. This iterative and collaborative development process
82 refined our approach. For instance, the screening questionnaire included twelve modifiable risk and
83 protective factors from the Lifestyle for BRAin health (LIBRA) index [6, 24] to identify respondents
84 with room for lifestyle improvement and experts assisted with setting inclusion cut-offs based on their
85 experience and research.

86 The follow-up questionnaire assessed socio-cognitive determinants derived from various theories to
87 achieve a comprehensive understanding of their impact [8, 25]. Definitions and measurement
88 instructions for behavioral determinant research informed the item development [26]. Insights from a
89 prior interview study [11] led to the development of items targeting behavior-specific determinants. For
90 example, interviewees frequently mentioned they did not enjoy cooking, which resulted in an item to
91 assess attitudes towards cooking. Expert think-aloud sessions and a pre-test with low SES individuals
92 supported further refinement of the items in terms of face and content validity.

93 ***2.2.1 The screening questionnaire***

94 The screening questionnaire, based on the LIBRA index, aimed to identify respondents who actively
95 engaged in one or more unhealthy lifestyle behaviors. This included physical inactivity, low adherence
96 to a Mediterranean diet, overconsumption of alcohol, smoking, and low engagement in social and
97 cognitive activities. The 9-item Rapid Assessment of Physical Activity (RAPA) [27] was used to
98 identify respondents who were physically inactive, according to Dutch recommendations of doing at
99 least 150 minutes of moderate-to-vigorous activity per week, spread over several days [28]. The 14-
100 item Mediterranean Diet Adherence Screener (MEDAS14; scores ranging from 0-14) [29] was utilized
101 to select respondents with low adherence to the Mediterranean Diet (i.e., score ≤ 5). According to Dutch
102 diet guidelines, the Mediterranean diet aligns with most recommendations by emphasizing high
103 consumption of vegetables, fruits, whole grain products, nuts, legumes, oils, unsaturated fats, poultry,
104 and fish as well as low intake of red or processed meat, high-fat dairy, hard fats, salt, and sugar-
105 sweetened beverages [30]. Two items from the Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT) [31,
106 32] were utilized to identify respondents who consumed more than 1 unit of alcohol per day on average.

107 Although research on dementia risk suggests higher alcohol intake as harmful (i.e., 14 to 21 units per
108 week), the approach used in this study aligns with existing recommendations in the Netherlands to
109 prevent disease in general [30]. Self-constructed items were employed to identify respondents who
110 smoked and to assess the number of cigarettes (or other tobacco products) they consumed daily [33].
111 Engagement in social and cognitive activities was assessed using a self-constructed list of 12 activities,
112 based on previous questionnaires used in research on dementia risk reduction [34]. Respondents were
113 classified as socially and cognitively inactive based on a <median-split of weekly activities within our
114 sample [33].

115 Other health-related modifiable risk factors included in LIBRA were assessed by asking respondents if
116 a doctor had ever informed them about having coronary heart disease, renal dysfunction, diabetes, high
117 cholesterol, hypertension, or depression [35]. Obesity (Body Mass Index, $BMI \geq 30$) was determined
118 using self-reported weight and height (i.e., $BMI = \text{kg}/\text{m}^2$).

119 *2.2.2 The follow-up questionnaire*

120 Respondents who actively engaged in one or more unhealthy lifestyle behaviors were invited to
121 participate in the follow-up questionnaire exploring socio-cognitive determinants of these behaviors.
122 The follow-up questionnaire employed self-constructed items assessing determinants separately for
123 physical activity, Mediterranean diet, alcohol intake, smoking, and engagement in social and cognitive
124 activities. All respondents completed items on physical activity, Mediterranean diet, and social and
125 cognitive activities because, to an extent, everyone engages in these behaviors. Items on alcohol and
126 smoking were only completed by participants who indicated to drink alcohol or smoke.

127 The follow-up questionnaire utilized tailored items for each lifestyle behavior to investigate potentially
128 relevant determinants. Overall, the following categories of socio-cognitive determinants were assessed
129 for each lifestyle behavior separately: (a) beliefs about engaging in sufficient levels of a particular
130 behavior, (b) intentions to change behavior, (c) attitudes, (d) risk perceptions, (e) social and
131 environmental influences, and (f) perceived behavioral control.

132

133 **2.5 Data analyses**

134 Distribution and spread were calculated for sample characteristics in SPSS. A summative LIBRA-score
135 was calculated, ranging from -5.9 to +12.7, with higher scores indicating a higher relative risk for
136 dementia [6]. Cross-tables were calculated to assess the extent to which respondents perceived they
137 engaged in sufficient levels of a specific lifestyle behavior, in comparison to Dutch lifestyle
138 recommendations, which served as cut-offs for inviting respondents for the follow-up questionnaire.

139 Per lifestyle behavior the most relevant determinants were identified using Confidence Interval-Based
140 Estimation of Relevance (CIBER) [12, 36]. CIBER was favored over regression analyses due to
141 potential distortion caused by theoretical overlap among determinants [37]. Utilizing diamond plots,
142 CIBER visualizes univariate distributions of items that measure socio-cognitive determinants and their
143 bivariate association with behavior [12]. These plots allow to identify the relevance of determinants
144 based on visual inspection and interpretation. Specifically, scoring distribution and means provide an
145 indication of the room for improvement at the determinant level [36]. In an intervention context, altering
146 a behavioral determinant is relevant only when there is room for improvement. For instance, enhancing
147 knowledge is meaningful if respondents have limited knowledge. Additionally, plotted zero-order
148 associations between determinants and behavior indicate if it is relevant to alter a determinant [36]. For
149 instance, increasing limited knowledge is only relevant if it is associated with healthier behavior.

150 The *CIBER* function is part of the R package *behaviorchange* [38]. We used the *binaryCIBER* function
151 to identify relevant socio-cognitive determinants for physical inactivity, given the outcome of RAPA is
152 binary (i.e., physically inactive versus physically active). For assessing determinants of the other
153 lifestyle behaviors, we employed the regular CIBER function, which uses continuous outcome scores.
154 Specifically, separate CIBER plots were calculated using summative outcome scores for Mediterranean
155 diet, weekly units of alcohol intake, daily number of tobacco products, and weekly social and cognitive
156 activities.

157 **2.6 Ethics**

158 The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Health, Medicine and Life
159 Sciences of Maastricht University, the Netherlands (FHML-REC/2022/064). Participants gave digital

160 consent and received a standard compensation through Flycatcher of €0.60 (≈\$0.65) for the screening
 161 questionnaire and €2.00 (≈\$2.18) for the follow-up questionnaire.

162

163 **2. Results**

164 The screening questionnaire was sent to 6,228 panel members and was completed by 4,104 respondents
 165 (65.9%). Of these respondents, 91.3% (n=3,746) reported at least one unhealthy lifestyle behavior
 166 (Table 1), while 65% (n=2,666) reported two or more. The follow-up questionnaire was sent to 3,746
 167 respondents and was completed by 81.6% (n=3,056).

Table 1. Respondent characteristics and risk factors (N=4,104)

<u>Age in years</u> , Mean (SD); min to max	59.1 (10.57); 40 to 79
<u>Gender</u> , male (%) /female (%)	1710 (41.7) / 2394 (58.3)
<u>Migration background</u> , N (%)	
First generation	158 (3.8)
Second generation	347 (8.5)
<u>Highest completed educational level¹</u> , N (%)	
Low	823 (20.1)
Medium	1545 (37.6)
High	1736 (42.3)
<u>LIBRA-factors</u> , N (%)	
Physical inactivity*	2172 (52.9%)
Low adherence to Mediterranean diet*	2237 (54.5%)
Overconsumption of alcohol*	1005 (24.5%)
Smoking*	456 (11.1%)
Low social and cognitive activity*	2057 (50.1%)
Coronary heart disease	652 (15.9%)
Renal dysfunction	84 (2.0%)
Diabetes	434 (10.6%)
High blood cholesterol	1257 (30.6%)
Obesity**	918 (22.4%)
Hypertension	1400 (34.1%)
Depression	734 (17.9%)
<u>LIBRA-score</u> , Mean (SD); min to max	
Percentiles, 25;50;75	0.35 (2.90); -5.9 to +10.6 -2.6; -0.5; 1.6

Note. Protective factors are inverted and represented as risk factors to enhance interpretability. ¹Based on educational classification (SOI 21) of Statistics Netherlands *Behaviors used to invite respondents for the follow-up questionnaire. **Calculated with data of 4,099 respondents.

168 **3.1 Perceptions about behavior versus lifestyle recommendations**

169 Cross-tables (Table 2) demonstrate that 39.4% of the respondents, whom we considered to be physically
 170 inactive, perceived that they engaged in sufficient levels of physical activity. For Mediterranean diet,
 171 this figure was 54.8%; for alcohol consumption, it was 43.2%; and for cognitive and social engagement,
 172 it was 51.5%.

Table 2. *Perceptions about behavior versus lifestyle recommendations*

Do you think you do enough weekly physical activity? (n = 3,065)		
	<u>Physically inactive, N (%)</u>	<u>Physically active, N (%)</u>
Yes	701 (39.4%)	985 (76.5%)
Somewhat	680 (38.2%)	256 (19.9%)
No	397 (22.3%)	46 (3.6%)
Do you think you eat healthy? (n = 3,065)		
	<u>Low Mediterranean diet, N (%)</u>	<u>Medium-high Mediterranean diet, N (%)</u>
Yes	1007 (54.8%)	943 (76.8%)
Somewhat	753 (41.0%)	273 (22.2%)
No	77 (4.2%)	12 (1.0%)
Do you think you overconsume alcohol? (n = 2,410)*		
	<u>Overconsumption of alcohol, N (%)</u>	<u>Regular consumption of alcohol, N (%)</u>
Yes	93 (11.1%)	4 (.2%)
Somewhat	384 (45.7%)	122 (5.5%)
No	363 (43.2%)	1444 (64.9%)
Do you think that you are socially and actively engaged in life? (n = 3,065)		
	<u>Low activities, N (%)</u>	<u>Medium-high activities, N (%)</u>
Yes	423 (51.5%)	1506 (67.1%)
Somewhat	321 (39.1%)	601 (26.8%)
No	77 (9.4%)	137 (6.1%)

Note. Physically inactive is less than 150 min of moderate or 60 min of vigorous activity spread over several days of the week. Low adherence to Mediterranean diet is a summative score ≤ 5 on the MEDAS14. Overconsumption of alcohol is drinking over 1 unit per day on average (these items were only completed by respondents who indicate to drink). Low activity is based on the lowest 25% of weekly social and cognitive activities.

173 **3.2 Interpretating CIBER-plots to indicate relevant behavioral determinants**

174 Figures 1 and 2 present the CIBER-plots, visualizing scoring distributions with scatterplots and means,
 175 and illustrating associations between determinants and outcome behavior. Tables with the underlying
 176 data are available in the Supplementary Files.

177 **3.2.1 Intentions to change lifestyle behavior**

178 Scoring distributions indicate respondents had moderate intentions to change lifestyle behaviors, with
179 scores averaging around 3 on a 5-point scale (Fig 1 and 2). Intentions to reduce future dementia risk
180 were slightly higher than general behavior change intentions. Despite this, the weak associations
181 between intentions and outcome behavior suggest restricted relevance.

182 **3.2.2 Attitudes**

183 Distributions and associations highlight the relevance of passion for cooking and pleasure from alcohol
184 or smoking (Fig 1 and 2). Scores for cooking passion average below 3 on a 5-point scale, indicating
185 room for improvement, which has a moderate positive association with a healthier diet. Scoring
186 distributions for pleasure derived from alcohol or smoking are above 3.5 on a 5-point scale, suggesting
187 an opportunity to reduce these positive attitudes, especially in light of their moderate to strong
188 associations with higher consumption levels.

189 **3.2.3 Risk perceptions**

190 Distributions show respondents had realistic risk perceptions about the negative effects of unhealthy
191 behavior on physical health, brain health, and dementia risk (Fig 1 and 2). Scores concentrate between
192 3 and 4 on a 5-point scale, indicating limited room for enhancement of these risk perceptions. Restricted
193 relevance is further supported by weak associations with outcome behaviors.

194 **3.2.4 Social influences**

195 Respondents viewed their diet as relatively healthy compared to others, with scores between 3 and 4 on
196 a 5-point scale (Fig 1 and 2). This indicates that there is room for improvement, considering that 54.5%
197 of the respondents had a low adherence to the Mediterranean diet. Similarly, there is room to improve
198 accurate perceptions regarding alcohol intake compared to others. Scores ranged mainly between 1 and
199 3 on a 5-point scale, while 24.5% of the respondents who indicated to drink alcohol exceeded the
200 recommended level.

201

202

203 **3.2.5 Behavioral control**

204 Across behaviors, perceived control was identified as the most relevant determinant (Fig 1 and 2). Mean
205 scores among physically inactive respondents fall below 3 on a 5-point scale, suggesting room for
206 improvement, while strong associations indicate that more control is associated with higher activity
207 levels. Although respondents felt in control of their eating behavior, they perceived less control over
208 initiating dietary changes, with scores averaging 3.5 on a 5-point scale. Higher perceived control was
209 moderately correlated with a healthier diet, which indicates relevance. Additionally, perceived control
210 over smoking cessation was low, as scores average around 2 on a 5-point scale. This underscores its
211 relevance, especially since higher perceived control towards cessation strongly correlates with less
212 smoking. In contrast to smoking, respondents perceived high control over alcohol intake, suggesting
213 limited room for enhancement.

214 **3.3 Explained variance**

215 The CIBER-plots had varying explanatory power (95% CI of R^2). The plot for alcohol intake had the
216 highest explanatory power ($R^2=38-45\%$), followed by smoking ($R^2=19-34\%$), physical activity
217 ($R^2=20-26\%$), and diet ($R^2=18-23\%$). The plot for social and cognitive activities had low explanatory
218 power ($R^2=3\%$ to 5%), with no determinants identified as relevant based on scoring distributions and
219 associations.

220 **4. Discussion**

221 **4.1 Key findings**

222 Most of our respondents had room for improvement in lifestyle behavior but were unaware about this
223 room for improvement. Other relevant socio-cognitive determinants identified are attitudes (i.e., limited
224 passion for cooking and deriving pleasure from alcohol or smoking), misperceptions on social
225 comparisons (i.e., overestimating healthy diet intake and underestimating alcohol intake), and low
226 perceived control over behavior change (i.e., being more physically active, diet improvements, and
227 smoking cessation).

228

229 *4.2 Interpretation*

230 Misconceptions about adhering to lifestyle recommendations can stem from insufficient awareness
231 about guidelines, combined with overestimation of healthy behaviors and an underestimation of
232 unhealthy ones. The Protection Motivation Theory provides a framework for understanding how these
233 misconceptions about behavior can reduce the motivation to change [39, 40] by influencing threat
234 appraisal (i.e., perceived susceptibility and severity) [41]. For instance, misconceptions about adhering
235 to recommendations may lead to lower perceived susceptibility, which decreases the inclination to act
236 [40]. This may explain why our respondents had limited intentions towards initiating change, which
237 aligns with other research showing only 32% of the physically inactive individuals, 18% of those not
238 adhering to diet recommendations, and 29% of high alcohol consumers have intentions to change [42].
239 Our findings further highlight the relevance of perceived behavioral control, a concept akin to self-
240 efficacy [41, 43]. Individuals who feel more in control over their behavior, particularly in overcoming
241 barriers [43], are more inclined to initiate behavior change [44]. However, many of our respondents
242 perceived to have limited control over initiating behavior change, potentially diminishing their
243 intentions. Notably, respondents who drank alcohol perceived high levels of control while
244 underestimating their consumption compared to others. These findings are consistent with earlier
245 indicators that drinkers are often overconfident about their ability to control alcohol intake [45], while
246 they overestimate others' and underestimate their own consumption levels [46].
247 Based on the findings, motivating individuals to reduce dementia risk through lifestyle changes should
248 prioritize enhancing accurate perceptions about behavior while strengthening behavioral control.
249 Individual-level interventions could use self-monitoring methods like measuring step count or
250 completing a food diary to decrease misconceptions about the adherence to recommendations. Self-
251 monitoring may already be a steppingstone towards positive lifestyle change, through the mere
252 measurement effect [47, 48]. Providing timely, individualized, non-punitive, and actionable feedback
253 may further encourage healthy lifestyle improvements by making individuals aware of their own
254 behavior and by providing specific cues to action [49, 50]. Goal setting and action planning methods
255 are also well-known methods to enhance perceived behavioral control, preferably by gradually

256 increasing the achievability of certain behavioral changes [30]. Formulating coping responses to
257 overcome specific barriers and cope with difficult situations may further facilitate goal achievement
258 [51]. In earlier qualitative research [11], we observed that low perceived control frequently resulted
259 from earlier failed attempts to change lifestyle behavior. This underscores the importance of providing
260 support to individuals who experience relapse, for example by encouraging them to view it as a part of
261 the behavior change process and use it as an opportunity to learn from the experience [52]. Based on
262 these findings, we strongly advocate for the adoption of specific, evidence-based behavior change
263 methods to support individuals with changing their lifestyles to reduce dementia risk. This requires
264 careful reconsideration of intervention elements to prioritize methods that are able to target relevant
265 socio-cognitive determinants to increase the likelihood of behavior change. For instance, by
266 emphasizing enjoyable cooking activities, drawing inspiration from successful programs [53] to make
267 participants enthusiastic about creating new eating habits.

268 While individual-level interventions are important, they must be supplemented by environmental-level
269 strategies to reduce dementia prevalence [54]. Although our sample is only partially representative of
270 the Dutch public, many of our participants had room to improve one or multiple lifestyle behaviors to
271 reduce their future risk of dementia. We observed slightly lower prevalence rates for unhealthy lifestyle
272 behaviors compared to the broader Dutch population [55], indicating that our results might understate
273 the potential for dementia risk reduction in the Netherlands. Given the high prevalence of both
274 unhealthy behavior and dementia, as well as the substantial impact of the environment on behavior, the
275 effectiveness of individual-level interventions alone is questionable [54]. Therefore, we advocate for a
276 multi-faceted approach that combines individual and environmental interventions to facilitate healthy
277 lifestyle behaviors and reduce the risk of dementia at the population level.

278 ***4.3 Practical applications***

279 The research findings are currently used to shape the development of individual-level behavior change
280 applications that are integrated in the digital LETHE intervention to prevent cognitive decline and
281 dementia [13]. LETHE utilizes a smartphone app and Fitbit smartwatch to monitor lifestyle behavior.
282 One of the features under development is a system to classify participants into weekly adherence

283 pathways (i.e., green, yellow, red). This system would enable lifestyle monitoring to offer personalized
284 digital and in person feedback and support. Furthermore, smartphone functionalities are under
285 development to empower participants to actively monitor a range of lifestyle behaviors. For instance,
286 through a weekly performance score with motivational feedback messages. These examples show how
287 the research findings can guide the development of individual-level applications to support behavior
288 change.

289 ***4.4 Strengths and limitations***

290 This cross-sectional study employed several measures to enhance credibility, including pre-registration
291 [17] of the protocol to ensure transparency and minimize reporting bias. All materials and data are
292 openly accessible, supporting reproducibility. A key strength of this study is the recruitment through
293 the research agency Flycatcher. Unlike health-related panels, Flycatcher surveys a wide range of topics,
294 including marketing and policy research. This helped us to reach a broad audience that is not only
295 interested in participating in health-related research. However, this approach might have introduced
296 selection bias because individuals who volunteer for panels may not accurately reflect the entire
297 population. For instance, individuals with limited digital skills might find it more challenging to
298 participate in an Internet-based panel. Although 80% of the Dutch public has basic digital skills [56]
299 this indicates a substantial part might be excluded from our research.

300 The study utilized a robust screening process with the validated LIBRA-index, but we relied on
301 unvalidated items to assess social and cognitive activities, which may have affected measurement
302 accuracy that limited the exploratory power. Additionally, future research is needed to explore the
303 determinants of social and cognitive activities more thoroughly and to investigate the impact of
304 environmental factors and demographic differences, particularly socio-economic status, on lifestyle
305 behavior in the context of dementia risk.

306 ***4.5 Conclusions***

307 Promoting lifestyle changes to reduce dementia risk is complex. Individual-level interventions that
308 encourage lifestyle change should prioritize enhancing accurate perceptions of lifestyle behaviors in

309 comparison to recommendations, while strengthening perceived control over initiating behavioral
310 changes.

311

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318 **Conflict of interest**

319 The authors have no conflict of interest to report.

320 **Data availability**

321 The materials and data supporting the conclusions are available on the Open Science Framework
322 through <https://osf.io/eqbgr/>.

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